

The Impact of Home Environment on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students

Komal Jain¹, Dr. Sarika Mohta²

¹Research Scholar, Career Point University, Kota, Rajasthan, India

²Associate Professor, Om Kothari Institute of Management & Research, Kota, Rajasthan, India

How to cite this paper: Komal Jain | Dr. Sarika Mohta "The Impact of Home Environment on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-4, June 2019, pp.808-811, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23910.pdf>

IJTSRD23910

ABSTRACT

The basic objective of this research is to study effect and correlation of home environment and academic achievement of 9th class students. Sample consists of 120 students and divided into 60 girls and 60 boys. 9th class students chosen from school of Kota city. Random sampling method was used to collect the data. Home Environment scale, developed by A. Akhtar and S.B. Saxena (2011) was used to see the home environment level in each student and Academic achievement analyse through the exam results of the student. A positive relation found between home environment and academic achievement of the students and there is no significant difference in home environment of boys and girls.

Keywords: home environment, academic achievement

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement is the performance of students in the field of education. Learning is the interaction between a learner and the environment if environment is favourable, the learner feels easy to learn and gets fully concentrate on their studies. Learning starts from home when child's born. Child learns a lot from the family in everyway. Home environment has great impact on Learning (dr.nimmimaria 2015) The home environment plays a major role to determining the child's personality and also in their achievement. (Jayanthi J. and Srinivasan K.2015) The home has an important influence on the child's academic achievement. What the child learns at home and how his family motivates him towards education contributes to the child's success in school, (Essien, 2002).

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

Child success is not a because of school and teachers it is also because of efforts of the parents and their home environment and child itself, Good education does not come about by chance. (jassar pappu2017)

Many of studies revealed that there is a positive relation between the home environment and academic achievement. (NIMMI MARIA 2015 Dr.Y.S.Deswal, Rekha Rani (2014) Jayanthi J. and Srinivasan K(2015),) there is a significant correlation between home environment on academic achievement of higher secondary students. (Dr.Lileydoley) analyse home environment, parental expectation, parental involvement, academic stimulation and parental encouragement significantly affect secondary school student's on their academic achievement. Results show a positive significant correlation between home environment and academic achievement of the students.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the academic achievement among secondary school boys and girls students.
2. To study the home environment among secondary school boys and girls students.
3. To see the effect of home Environment on academic achievement among secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS

1. There is no significant difference of academic achievement among boys and girl.
2. There is no significant difference in home environment among secondary school boys and girl students
3. There is correlation between home environment and academic achievement among secondary School students.

METHOD

The study was conducted on 120 students of class 9th those were studying info Kota city, Rajasthan. The sample of 120 students was divided in 60 girls and 60 boys for the study. The sample was selected through random sampling. The home environment scale used for analyse the level of home environment and school score card (mark sheet) taken for the analyse the academic achievement.

VARIABLES

1. Independent Variable: home environment and academic achievement
2. Dependent Variable: gender

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

For testing the hypothesis mean, standard deviation, p- value & Pearson correlation were calculated and presented in different tables using Microsoft excel

PROCEDURE

After giving questionnaire, purpose, rules and procedure of the study was explained to the subjects and the responses sheets were collected back after the allotted time.

Home environment scale - For the assess of home environment of a child researcher use home environment scale (HES-AASS) which is developed by A.Akhtar and S.B

Saxena (2011) this scale normally takes about 15-20 minutes. there are five responses 'ALWAYS', 'OFTEN', 'SOMETIMES', 'LEAST' and 'NEVER'. 4 marks for 'Always', 3 marks for 'Often', 2 marks for 'Sometimes', 1 marks for 'LEAST', 0 for 'NEVER' responses for positive items and the scoring will be reverse for the negative items. The range of score could be 50-200. More score shows the better home environment.

NORMS FOR INTERPRETATION OF LEVEL OF HOME ENVIRONMENT

S. No.	Range of Z-Scores	Grade	Level of home environment	Score Range for both sex
1.	+2.01 and above	A	Extremely favorable	180-187
2	+1.26 to +2.00	B	Highly favorable	162-179
3	+0.51 to +1.25	C	Above average favorable	143-161
4	-0.50 to +0.50	D	Average/moderately favorable	94-142
5	-0.51 to 1.25	E	Unfavorable	93-83
6	-1.26 to 2.00	F	Highly unfavorable	82-81
7	-2.01 and below	G	Extremely unfavorable	80-76

INTERPRETATION OF LEVEL OF HOME ENVIRONMENT

S. No.	Range of Z-Scores	Grade	Level of home environment	No of students	PERCENTAGE
1.	+2.01 and above	A	Extremely favorable	NIL	NIL
2	+1.26 to +2.00	B	Highly favorable	13	10.8%
3	+0.51 to +1.25	C	Above average favorable	37	30.8%
4	-0.50 to +0.50	D	Average/moderately favorable	69	57.5%
5	-0.51 to -1.25	E	Unfavorable	1	0.8%
6	-1.26 to -2.00	F	Highly unfavorable	NIL	NIL
7	-2.01 and below	G	Extremely unfavorable	NIL	NIL

INTERPRETATION

The whole sample of the students divided into different level of home environment; based on the z scores we see the range of the home environment. In the manual which is divided into 7 levels of home environment- 1) extremely favorable (grade A) (180-187), 2) Highly favorable Grade B (162-179), 3) Above average favourable, grade C (143-161), 4) Average/moderately favorable, Grade D (94-142) 5) Unfavorable, Grade E (93-83) 6) Highly unfavorable, Grade F (82-81) 7) Extremely unfavorable, Grade G (80-76) according to this division scores falls under the category

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT**GRADING SYSTEM USED**

The overall performance of the students was graded as with reference to the marks obtained in the test/exams held in that academic year, for convenience of data analysis.

1. > 80% - excellent
2. > 60-79% - good
3. 50-59% - average
4. 35-49% - poor
5. < 35% - very poor

MARKS RANGE		GRADE	GRADE POINT
90.1	100	A1	10.0
80.1	90	A2	9.0
70.1	80	B1	8.0
60.1	70	B2	7.0
50.1	60	C1	6.0
40.1	50	C2	5.0
30.1	40	D	4.0
20.1	30	E1	3.0
0	20	E2	2.0

S. NO	STUDENT CATEGOTRY	TOTAL STUDENT	NO OF STUDENT IN excellent category	No of students in good category	No of students in average category	No.of students in poor category	No.of students in very poor category
1	boys	60	19	24	8	9	NIL
2	girls	60	25	22	8	5	NIL
3	boys and girls	120	44	46	16	14	NIL

SCORING

Scoring was done according to the scoring scheme of the tool given in the manual; in this way every subject obtained an score on home environment scale. Scoring was done according to the scoring scheme of the tool given in the manual; in this way every subject obtained score on home environment scale.

RESULTS

OBJECTIVE - "To study the effects of home Environment and academic achievement among secondary school students"

SN.	N		Raw Score Mean (Home Environment)	Ranges of Z Score	Interpretation	Raw Score Mean (Academic Achievement)	Interpretation
1	120	Combine	138.7	0.50to+0.50	Average favorable	71.03	good

From above table 1.1 reveals that the overall home environment data of 120 students raw score is 16655 and total (boys & girls) mean score is 138.7 and range of z score is (0.50 to +0.50) which is in the average/moderately favourable category it shows students are having average home environment.

From above table the overall academic achievement data of 120 students was calculated, that overall girls and boys mean score is 70.2 which is fall in the good category.

H-1 - "There is no significant difference of home environment among boys and girl": is accepted

H-2 -- There is no significant difference in academic achievement among boys and girl: is accepted

Table 2.1

S.No.		N	Mean	SD	p-value	Level of Significance at (0.05)
Home environment	Boys	60	137.16	18.38	0.3	No significant difference
	Girls	60	140.41	19.34		
Academic achievement	Boys	60	68.9	16.40	0.15	No significant difference
	Girls	60	73.1	15.50		

From above table the mean score of boys are 137.16 and for girls are 140.41 The Standard deviation is respectively 18.38 and 19.34 with the mean difference of .96. The calculated p-value is 0.3 which is higher than 0.05. Therefore, we can conclude that there is no significant difference in home environment among boys and girls. Lily doley (2017) also conclude there is no significant difference in boys and girls. It means hypothesis is accepted.

From the above table the mean score of boys is 68.9 and for girls are 73.1 and standard deviation for boys and girls are 16.40 and 15.50 and the calculated p value is 0.15 which is higher than 0.05. it mean there is no significance difference in academic achievement of boys and girl secondary students

OBJECTIVE 3- TO SEE THE EFFECT OF HOME ENVIORNMENT ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

	Home environment		Academic achievement		
	MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD	TEST
Highly favorable & above average favorable(49)	156.62	7.2784	77.1	12.65	0.00
Unfavorable (69)	126.05	13.46	65.3	19.24	0.00

On the basis of table we can see there is a correlation between home environment and academic achievement .if child is having favourable Home environment academic achievement will be high.if child is having unfavourable environment it effects their academic achievement and they gets low academic achievement. In the favourable environment mean score of academic achievement is 77.1 and SD is 12.6 and in the unfavourable environment mean score of the students is 65.1 and SD is 19.24. on the basis of means we can say academic achievement is low if home environment is not favourable

H-4 The correlation between home environment and academic achievement among secondary school students.

Table 3.1

Home Environment	Academic achievement(Combine))	
	Pearson correlation	0.41
	Sig.(2tailed)	0.00
	N	120
Home Environment Boys	Academic achievement (boys)	
	Pearson correlation	0.61
	Sig.(2tailed)	0.00
	N	60
Home Environment Girls	Academic achievement (girls)	
	Pearson correlation	0.18
	Sig.(2tailed)	0.00
	N	60

From the above table it can be concluded that home environment and academic achievement is correlated to each other in total boys. And interpretation of results shows that p value is 0.00 in the level of 0.01. and Pearson correlation value between home environment and academic achievement is 0.41 which is significant.

From the above table it can be concluded that home environment and academic achievement is correlated to each other in total boys and interpretation of results shows that p value is 0.00 in the level of 0.01 and Pearson correlation value between self esteem and emotional intelligence is 0.61 which is significant.

From the above table it can be concluded that home environment and academic achievement is correlated to each other in total girls and interpretation of results shows that p value is 0.00 in the level of 0.01. Dr. Y. S. Deswal, Rekha Rani, Savita Ahlawat (2014), Jayanthi J. and Srinivasan K.(2015) also assess that there is a correlation between home environment and academic achievement and Pearson correlation value between self esteem and emotional intelligence is 0.18 which is significant.

CONCLUSION

The present study reveals that the boys and girls secondary students having no significant difference in their home environment and there is no significant difference in academic achievement in secondary school students and it is also analysed there is a correlation between home environment and academic achievement among boys and girls.

REFERENCE

- [1] Jayanti.j(2015),influence of home environment on academic achievement in mathematics. IOSR journal of methematics.11(4).26-31
- [2] Pappattu. j (2017).a study on family environment and its effect on academic achievement in science among secondary school students. International journal of research-granthaalatah.5(6)2394-3629
- [3] Maria.N.(2015).home environment and academic achievement of students at higher secondary level. international journal of current research.7(7).18745-18747
- [4] Deswal.Y.(2014).impact of home environment on academic achievement of adolescent students in relation to their locality and type of school. bhartiyaam international journal of education & research. 3(3). 2277-1255

